

PROSPECTS OF USING COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Аннотация. В данной статье описаны важные перспективы использования цифровых технологий в процессе обучения студентов и преподавателей и их влияние на будущие направления образования.

Annotation. This article describes the important perspectives of the use of digital technologies in the learning process for students and teachers and their impact on the future directions of education.

Ключевые слова. Современное образование, цифровые технологии, интерактивные уроки, инновации, креативные идеи.

Keywords. Modern education, digital technologies, interactive lessons, innovation, creative ideas.

Modern education is a terminological subject that represents the future educational systems and methods of the 21st century. Modern education consists of new methods aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills based on critical thinking and practice.

There are several main features of modern education:

-modern education ensures that students work in mutual cooperation aimed at self-mastery and self-development. In the educational center, students will have the opportunity to put their knowledge into practice, find solutions to problems and actively participate in the social environment.

- in modern education, students learn to participate in learning and mastering processes based on mutual cooperation and community. It is used in group work, consultation and mutual support.

- technology is used at a high level in modern education. Technologies such as the Internet, computers, interactive textbooks, presentations, videos, etc. serve to make the educational process interesting, interactive and effective.

- in modern education, students develop the ability to understand, discuss, find solutions to problems and create new ideas. It focuses on their creativity and innovation.

- in modern education, students are directed to self-development and put their mastery into practice. It is aimed at students learning from their own mistakes, expressing independent opinions and setting personal goals.

-modern education is aimed at students to analyze, apply and learn real-world issues. It is aimed at students to find solutions to problems in life and develop practice rather than learning knowledge about a particular subject or field.

Modern education represents the changes related to the reforms and developments of education and aims at students' independent, effective and social mastery. This allows them to find their unique place in the world, express their thoughts and benefit society.

Below are some examples of the prospects for using digital technologies in modern education:

- digital technologies provide great opportunities for organizing interactive lessons. Smart boards, projectors, interactive textbooks, tablets and computers help teachers to make learning more interesting. During the lesson, students will be able to complete interactive tasks, watch short videos, read the lesson material and leave comments.

- digital technologies increase online learning opportunities for students and teachers. Through video conferencing, online classes and databases, teachers will be able to teach and assess students remotely.

- digital technologies allow to make the learning process of students more interesting with the help of games and simulators. Through virtual games and simulators, students will be able to put theoretical knowledge into practice. This increases students' motivation and makes them more engaged in the learning process.

- high-quality database through digital technologies gives students freedom. Students will be able to independently develop their skills through Internet searches, electronic libraries, articles, videos, and other electronic resources.

- digital technologies allow the development of adaptive educational systems and programs. These systems provide personalized learning for students. The student is taught new material according to his level of knowledge or given tasks that help to solve problems.

- digital technologies help to increase the cooperative learning process of students. Students can learn to contribute and work in a team by working together. Spreadsheet and workbook integration systems encourage cooperative student work and collaborative team or remote work.

Digital technologies increase students' interests in school education, make the learning process more interesting and facilitate learning. These perspectives suggest that the use of digital technologies in school education can further enhance the activities and develop the skills of students.

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